

that in the 700,000 ha of irrigated rice land in Rio Grande do Sul and Santa Catarina states. Throughout the uplands rice is commonly cultivated as a *grub crop* after the land has been cleared. It generally gives way to corn, soybean, cotton, or pasture in the third year. This type of *grub farming* appears to be short-lived.

Rice research priorities have been determined by the Brazilian Agricultural Research Indicative Plan for 1980 to 1985 (see table). Research projects for 1979 are being developed either by the 11 EMBRAPA units or by the 10 state cooperative institutions. ■

Ten IRTP monitoring tours in 1978

The International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) sponsored 10 monitoring tours in 1978 to enable rice scientists from various countries to observe how materials from different sources perform in the international nurseries and to become better acquainted with other rice research in their regions. The IRTP continued the trend of making the monitoring tours coincide with workshops or planning sessions, which gives scientists the opportunity to observe the problems first-hand in the field under different conditions immediately before discussing them at the workshops.

The monitoring tour to South India and Sri Lanka coincided with a planning meeting held at Peradeniya, Sri Lanka, to finalize plans for the 1978 nurseries. The Rainfed Rice Monitoring Tour to Indonesia preceded the International Rice Research Conference at IRRI, which focused on rainfed rice. The Deepwater Rice Monitoring Tour preceded the International Workshop on Deepwater Rice held in Calcutta in August. Likewise, the Cold Tolerance Monitoring Tour was tied up with the Cold Tolerance Workshop in Korea, jointly sponsored by IRTP and Korea's Office of Rural Development. In West Africa the first regional monitoring tour was linked with a West African Rice Development Association (WARDA) Workshop held in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Plans for many future IRTP nurseries are finalized during the monitoring tours.

Scientists are also able to see the strengths and weaknesses in various national rice research programs.

Monitoring tours in 1978 and scientists who participated are listed below:

South India/Sri Lanka 30 January–9 February
 Bangladesh – M. S. Ahmad, D.G. Kanter
 India – K. M. Bala Subramaniam, M. Dagg, K. I. James, V. T. John, M. B. Kalode
 Indonesia – H. M. Beachell, B. H. Siwi
 Sri Lanka – I. Gunawardena, D. Jayawardena, A. D. Somapala
 Thailand – Sermasak Awakul
 IRRI – E. A. Heinrichs, H. E. Kauffman, G. S. Khush, E. M. Mendoza, T. W. Mew, D. V. Seshu

Southern Region of South America 6–20 March
 Argentina – W. Jetter
 Brazil – P. S. Carmona, D. M. De Souza, J.F.V. Moraes
 Colombia – M. J. Rosero, H. Weeraratne
 Peru – J. Fernandez
 IRRI – H. E. Kauffman, J.C. O'Toole

Rainfed Rice 7–14 April
 India – S. Biswas
 Indonesia – H. Anwarhan, H. M. Beachell, I. Manwan, B. H. Siwi, D. M. Tantera
 Malaysia – Chen Yok Hwa
 Philippines – A. Bueno
 Thailand – B. Somrith
 IRRI – J. S. Nanda, R. C. Saxena

Observations on Deepwater Rice in Thailand, Bangladesh, and India 9–16 August
 Bangladesh – B. A. Dewan, D. G. Kanter, M. Nasiruddin
 India – C. H. Misra
 Indonesia – H. Anwarhan
 Thailand – Chai Prechachat, B. R. Jackson, Nopporn Supapoj

IRRI – D. V. Seshu
Cold Tolerance 7–19 September
 India – A. R. Hamdani, J. P. Tandon
 Indonesia – H. M. Beachell, Z. Harahap
 Japan – M. Shibata
 Korea – J. H. Lee
 Nepal – M. H. Heu, B. B. Shahi
 Philippines – A. Ronduen
 Taiwan – L. F. Lee
 IRRI – H. E. Kauffman, J. S. Nanda, B. S. Vergara

Rice Improvement Activities in Four West African Countries 30 September–7 October
 Liberia – M. A. Choudhury
 Nigeria – A. O. Abifarin, S. O. Fagade
 Sierra Leone – R. A. D. Jones, I. C. Mahapatra
 IRRI – D. V. Seshu

Observations on Rice Improvement in the Indus River Plains of Pakistan and India 1–9 October
 Pakistan – M. Akbar, I. M. Bhatti, A. Majid, V. E. Ross
 India – O. P. Meelu, H. N. Shahi, G. S. Sidhu
 IRRI – G. S. Khush

Yield and Observational Nurseries with Focus on Long-Duration Rice 27 October–6 November
 Bangladesh – N. M. Miah
 India – R. K. Misra, J. R. K. Rao, R. A. Thakur
 Thailand – K. Varaporn
 IRRI – D. V. Seshu

Observations on Rice Virus Diseases in Indonesia, Thailand, and India 27 October–7 November
 India – A. Anjaneyulu, A. Ghosh
 Bangladesh – A. K. M. Shahjahan
 Indonesia – P. S. Rao, Nasir Saleh
 IRRI – H. E. Kauffman, K. C. Ling

Breeding for Drought Resistance in Northern and Eastern India and Northeast Thailand 24 September–2 October
 India – M. J. B. Rao, S. C. Prasad
 IRRI – T. T. Chang, J. C. O'Toole ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Jeerakasala — a tall scented rice variety in Kerala, India

N. N. Ramankutty, associate professor, Agronomic Research Station, Chalakudy, and U.P. Bhaskaran, director of research, Kerala Agricultural University (KAU), Vellanikkara, Trichur, Kerala, India

Jeerakasala, a tall, scented rice variety, grows 976 m above sea level in the high ranges of Kerala, known as Wynad. Its white, fine grain gives off a pleasing

aroma when cooking — a trait that makes Jeerakasala popular for the preparation of the delicacy *biriyani*. Jeerakasala is also known as *biriyani rice*.

The scent can be detected even in the field when the crop is flowering. The variety brings a premium market price — sometimes more than double that of ordinary varieties.

The photoperiod-sensitive variety is usually sown in June and transplanted in